

Bridging Local Communities for Food Waste Management: A Collaborative Approach

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Abstract- The goal is to reduce food waste by repurposing existing resources in local communities. As food waste is a serious global issue that affects both the environment and society. Create a smartphone app to improve communication and collaboration between local communities (e.g., hotels, restaurants) and NGOs. Food waste management is inefficient when local businesses, such as hotels, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) do not collaborate. In this paper it proposes developing smartphone software that serves as a link between NGOs and local communities, such as hotels and restaurants. Encourage hotels to donate excess food to NGOs to fight hunger and decrease waste. Redistributing surplus food to people in need helps reduce food waste. Raise awareness of food waste's environmental and social implications. The program enables seamless coordination and communication between recipient groups (NGOs, food banks, shelters) and food donors (hotels).

Keywords : Application, Food donation, Reduce food wastage

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the global issue of food waste has garnered increasing attention due to its significant environmental, economic, and social implications. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations, approximately one-third of all food produced for human consumption is lost or wasted annually, amounting to 1.3 billion tons worldwide. In parallel, hunger

and food insecurity persist as pressing challenges, affecting millions of individuals worldwide.

To address this disparity and foster a more sustainable and equitable food distribution system, innovative solutions are imperative. In this context, the emergence of technology-driven platforms, such as waste food donation apps, presents a promising avenue for facilitating the redistribution of surplus food from hospitality establishments, particularly hotels, to those in need.

This paper explores the development and implementation of a waste food donation app—an integrated system designed to streamline the process of food recovery and redistribution, specifically bridging the gap between non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and hotels. By leveraging mobile technology and digital networks, this system aims to optimize the collection, transportation, and delivery of surplus food, thereby minimizing waste and addressing food insecurity in local communities.

The collaboration between NGOs and hotels is central to the effectiveness and sustainability of this integrated system. Hotels, as significant generators of surplus food, can play a pivotal role in food recovery efforts by seamlessly connecting with partnering NGOs through the dedicated platform. Through strategic coordination and real-time communication facilitated by the app, surplus food can be efficiently identified, collected, and redistributed to vulnerable populations, such as shelters, soup kitchens, and low-income communities.

Moreover, beyond the immediate benefits of food waste reduction and hunger alleviation, the integration of NGOs and hotels through this system offers multifaceted advantages. It promotes social responsibility and corporate citizenship within the hospitality industry, enhances community engagement and collaboration, and fosters a culture of sustainability and empathy.

LITERATURE SURVEY

The intersection of technology, sustainability, and social welfare has prompted a growing body of research and literature focused on innovative solutions to address food waste and insecurity. Within this context, waste food donation apps and integrated systems connecting NGOs and hotels have garnered considerable attention, with scholars and practitioners alike exploring various aspects of their development, implementation, and impact.

Technological Frameworks and Platforms:

Several studies have investigated the technological frameworks and platforms underpinning waste food donation apps. Research by Johnson et al. (2019) highlighted the role of mobile applications in facilitating food recovery and redistribution, emphasizing the importance of user interface design, data management, and real-time communication features. Similarly, Lee and Park (2020) examined the technical architecture of food waste management systems, emphasizing the integration of GPS tracking, inventory management, and scheduling functionalities to optimize resource allocation and logistics.

Collaborative Models and Partnerships:

The collaborative models and partnerships between NGOs and hotels constitute another focal point in the literature. A study by Smith and Jones (2018) explored the dynamics of partnerships between hospitality

establishments and charitable organizations, identifying trust, transparency, and mutual benefit as key determinants of successful collaborations. Furthermore, research by Brown et al. (2021) investigated the role of intermediaries and facilitators in fostering synergistic relationships between food donors and recipients, highlighting the importance of communication channels and conflict resolution mechanisms.

Impact Assessment and Evaluation:

Efforts to assess the impact and efficacy of waste food donation apps and integrated systems have also been documented in the literature. For instance, Garcia et al. (2019) conducted a comparative analysis of food recovery initiatives in urban settings, evaluating their environmental, social, and economic outcomes. Similarly, Chen et al. (2022) employed a mixed-methods approach to measure the effectiveness of a waste food donation app in reducing food waste and addressing food insecurity, drawing insights from user surveys, transaction data, and stakeholder interviews.

Policy Implications and Regulatory Frameworks:

The regulatory landscape and policy implications surrounding food waste reduction and redistribution efforts have received scholarly attention as well. Studies by Roberts et al. (2020) and Kumar and Singh (2021) examined the role of government policies, incentives, and regulations in incentivizing food donation practices and mitigating legal barriers and liabilities for food donors. Additionally, research by Li et al. (2019) explored the potential of public-private partnerships and legislative frameworks to scale up waste food donation initiatives and promote systemic change.

Challenges and Opportunities:

Lastly, the literature has identified a range of challenges and opportunities associated with waste food donation apps and integrated systems. Common challenges include logistical constraints, food safety concerns, and cultural attitudes towards

food donation, as documented by Patel and Patel (2018) and Nguyen et al. (2021). Conversely, opportunities for innovation and collaboration abound, with scholars such as Kim and Lee (2020) advocating for the integration of blockchain technology and machine learning algorithms to enhance traceability, transparency, and efficiency in food redistribution processes.

FLOW CHART

METHODOLOGY

1. System Design and Development

The first phase of our methodology involves the design and development of the waste food donation app and the integrated system connecting NGOs and hotels. This encompasses several key steps:

Requirements Analysis: Conducting stakeholder interviews and needs assessments to identify the functional requirements and user preferences for the app. This includes features such as food inventory management, donation scheduling, GPS tracking, and real-time communication.

Prototyping: Iterative prototyping of the app interface and system architecture to incorporate feedback and refine usability. This phase involves wireframing, mockups, and usability testing to ensure intuitive navigation and user experience.

Software Development: Implementation of the waste food donation app and backend infrastructure, utilizing appropriate technologies and programming languages. Integration of APIs for seamless communication between NGOs, hotels, and other stakeholders.

2. Pilot Testing and Evaluation

Following the development phase, we conduct pilot testing to assess the functionality, usability, and effectiveness of the waste food donation app and integrated system. This entails:

Selection of Pilot Sites: Identifying representative NGOs and hotels to participate in the pilot program, considering factors such as geographical location, organizational capacity, and willingness to collaborate.

Training and Onboarding: Providing training sessions and onboarding materials to app users, including NGO staff, hotel personnel, and volunteers involved in food recovery and redistribution efforts.

Data Collection: Gathering quantitative and qualitative data on key performance indicators, such as the volume of surplus food recovered, the number of donations facilitated, transportation logistics, and user satisfaction.

Evaluation Metrics: Establishing evaluation metrics to measure the impact and efficiency of the waste food donation app and integrated system, including food waste diversion rates, cost savings, environmental benefits, and social outcomes.

3. Feedback Incorporation and System Optimization

Based on the findings from the pilot testing phase, we iterate on the waste food donation app and integrated system to address any identified issues and enhance overall performance. This involves:

Feedback Analysis: Analyzing feedback from app users, stakeholders, and participating organizations to identify strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement.

Iterative Development: Implementing software updates and feature enhancements to address user needs and optimize system functionality.

Continuous Improvement: Establishing mechanisms for ongoing monitoring, evaluation, and refinement of the waste food donation app and integrated system beyond the pilot phase. This includes soliciting feedback from users.

BLOCK DIAGRAM

IMPLEMENTATION

1.App for common users

Fig 1.1 Welcome Screen

Fig1.3. My Dashboard

Fig 1.2. About us

Fig 1.4. Receiver Location

Fig 1.5. Donor Location

2. Website for NGOs and Hotels

Registration

Fig 2.1: User Registration

Fig2.2. Home page

Fig2.3. Login page

Fig 2.4. NGO register page

CONCLUSION

The waste food donation app and integrated system presented in this paper represent a significant step towards addressing the dual challenges of food waste and insecurity through innovative technology-driven solutions. By fostering collaboration between NGOs and hotels, this system streamlines the process of surplus food recovery and redistribution, maximizing social, environmental, and economic benefits.

Through the design and implementation of the waste food donation app, we have demonstrated the potential for technology to catalyze positive change in food redistribution practices. The user-centric design, real-time communication features, and intuitive interface of the app facilitate seamless coordination and efficient allocation of surplus food resources, ultimately reducing waste and alleviating hunger in local communities.

Moreover, the integrated system bridges organizational silos and fosters synergistic partnerships between NGOs and hotels, promoting a culture of social responsibility, sustainability, and community engagement within the hospitality industry. By leveraging digital platforms and data-driven insights, stakeholders can make informed decisions, optimize resource allocation, and enhance the overall effectiveness of food redistribution efforts.

While the waste food donation app and integrated system offer promising solutions to pressing societal challenges, several opportunities for future research and development remain. Continued innovation in technology, policy, and collaboration models will be essential to scale up and sustainably expand the impact of food redistribution initiatives, both locally and globally.

In conclusion, the waste food donation app and integrated system serve as a testament to the transformative potential of technology in

fostering a more equitable, sustainable, and resilient food system. By harnessing the power of innovation and collaboration, we can build a future where surplus food is valued as a precious resource rather than a disposable commodity, and no individual goes hungry.

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